

DESIGN AND ANALYSIS OF A PALM NUT, KERNEL, AND SHELL SEPARATOR USING QUADRATIC PROJECTILE DRAG PRINCIPLES

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Abstract: Separating cracked palm nut components kernel, shell, and uncracked nut is challenging due to overlapping physical properties. This study presents the design and analysis of a separator based on the quadratic projectile drag principle, exploiting differences in mass, density, and drag-to-mass ratio to achieve spatial separation via controlled projectile motion under air resistance. Numerical simulations were performed at two initial velocities (10 m/s and 15 m/s) and five launch angles (10°, 20°, 30°, 40°, 45°). Projectile motion equations with quadratic air drag were solved to determine component trajectories and identify optimal separation conditions. At 10 m/s, separation was minimal at low angles (10°–20°) but improved at 30°–40° due to extended flight time enhancing drag differentiation; 45° produced maximum range but increased kernel-nut overlap. At 15 m/s, 30° yielded the clearest separation: shells landed first, nuts at intermediate distance, and kernels farthest. Higher angles (40°–45°) caused trajectory convergence, reducing separation efficiency. The findings demonstrate that projectile separation governed by quadratic drag is feasible for palm nut processing. A 30° launch at 15 m/s is optimal, providing a scientific basis for aerodynamic design and mechanical optimization. Implementing this approach can significantly increase separation efficiency, reduce kernel loss, and enhance the productivity of palm nut processing operations.

Keywords: Palm kernel, separation, projectile motion, quadratic drag, aerodynamic simulation, kernel recovery

1. Introduction

Palm kernel oil (PKO), extracted from the kernel of the oil palm (*Elaeis guineensis*), has witnessed a significant increase in global demand over the past decades due to its versatility and wide industrial applications [24]. With a high lauric acid content of approximately 50%, PKO is an essential raw material in the manufacture of soaps, detergents, cosmetics, confectioneries, pharmaceuticals, and biofuels [9]. Apart from coconut oil, it is the only major vegetable oil with such a high lauric acid composition, reinforcing its strategic value in both local and international markets.

Nigeria is endowed with abundant oil palm resources and was historically one of the leading exporters of palm kernel products, accounting for a significant share of global trade in the early 1960s [17]. However, a national economic shift toward petroleum exports in the 1970s reduced the competitiveness of palm products. Despite this decline, the palm kernel industry remains a vital contributor to Nigeria's economy, especially in the southern region, supporting agro-processing industries and small- to medium-scale enterprises [19]. Recent initiatives by

both government and private sectors to revitalize palm processing highlight the need for efficient mechanized systems to enhance productivity and product quality.

The extraction of PKO involves sequential operations including fruit sterilization, stripping, digestion, oil pressing, nut recovery, cracking, and separation [7]. While cracking technologies such as roller and centrifugal impact crackers are widely used, they primarily focus on shell removal and often produce a heterogeneous mixture of kernels, shells, and uncracked nuts [21]. The subsequent separation stage remains a major bottleneck. Manual picking, still practiced in rural communities, is labor-intensive, time-consuming, and unsuitable for large-scale production. Existing mechanical separators often fail to achieve optimal kernel recovery, resulting in product losses and reduced processing efficiency.

The physical and aerodynamic properties of palm nut components—differences in mass, density, size, and drag-to-mass ratio—offer a scientific basis for improved separation techniques [18]. Leveraging these differences, this study introduces a novel separation concept based on the quadratic projectile drag principle. Unlike conventional gravity- or density-based methods, this approach subjects cracked components to controlled projectile motion, allowing aerodynamic drag forces to influence their trajectories differently. By carefully selecting projection velocity and launch angle, components can be spatially separated as they land at distinct horizontal distances.

The primary objectives of this research are to:

1. Evaluate existing palm nut separation technologies and their limitations.
2. Determine the relevant physical and aerodynamic properties of palm nut components.
3. Develop a theoretical model incorporating quadratic air resistance to predict trajectories.
4. Simulate the effect of projection velocity and launch angle on component separation.
5. Propose a conceptual design for an integrated cracker–separator unit using locally available materials to enhance affordability, maintainability, and adaptability.

Focusing on theoretical modeling, simulation, and conceptual design, this study provides a scientific and engineering foundation for aerodynamic separation of palm nut components. The expected outcomes include improved kernel recovery efficiency, reduced post-cracking losses, and support for the sustainable growth and mechanization of the palm kernel industry in Nigeria and other palm-producing regions.

2. Literature Review

2.1 Overview of Palm Kernel Oil Production

Palm kernel oil (PKO) production involves a sequence of mechanical and thermal operations designed to recover oil from the kernel of the oil palm (*Elaeis guineensis*). The main stages include palm nut drying, cracking, kernel cleaning, preheating (roasting), crushing, oil expression, clarification, and storage. Each stage significantly influences the efficiency and quality of the extracted oil [6, 22].

Drying reduces moisture content, facilitating effective shell breakage during cracking while minimizing kernel damage. Cracking separates the kernel from the hard shell (endocarp) and can be achieved manually or mechanically. Traditional cracking with stones or mallets, though low cost, is labor intensive and inconsistent, making it unsuitable for large-scale production [2, 14].

After cracking, kernels are cleaned to remove contaminants such as stones and debris, which can damage downstream equipment or reduce oil quality [22]. Preheating improves oil yield during pressing, while crushing and flaking increase surface area for efficient extraction. Oil expression is commonly achieved using screw presses, where a rotating worm shaft forces the conditioned kernel meal through a perforated barrel, allowing oil

to drain while discharging the residual cake [6]. The expressed oil is clarified through filtration or screening before storage [23].

Despite advancements in extraction technology, cracking and separation remain critical determinants of kernel recovery efficiency because inefficiencies in these operations cascade into reduced oil yield [3].

2.2 Palm Nut Cracking Processes

Palm nut cracking aims to break the hard shell without damaging the kernel, maximizing recovery while minimizing breakage and equipment wear. Inefficient cracking results in incomplete shell removal, kernel fragmentation, and reduced extraction efficiency [11].

2.2.1 Traditional Methods

Manual cracking using stones or wooden mallets has been historically common. While simple and low cost, this method is slow, inconsistent, and unsuitable for industrial production [2, 14]. It remains prevalent in smallholder or rural communities with limited access to mechanization.

2.2.2 Mechanical Cracking Techniques

Mechanical crackers apply impact, compression, or shear forces. Principal systems include:

Centrifugal Impact Crackers: Nuts are hurled against stationary surfaces by high-speed rotors. Efficiency depends on rotor speed, nut size, and feed rate [11].

Roller Crackers: Nuts are crushed between counter-rotating rollers with adjustable clearance for controlled breakage [4].

Hammer Mills: Nuts are struck by swinging hammers at high speed, producing high cracking efficiency (up to ~98%), though often with increased kernel breakage [11].

Mechanical cracking produces a heterogeneous mixture of kernels, shells, and uncracked nuts, necessitating effective separation processes to recover kernels efficiently [1].

2.3 Palm Nut Separation Processes

Separation of cracked palm nut mixtures remains a challenge in PKO processing. Techniques exploit differences in density, size, shape, and aerodynamic properties.

2.3.1 Manual Sorting

Hand-picking kernels from shells is effective for small-scale operations but labor intensive and inefficient for large volumes [13, 1].

2.3.2 Clay Water Bath (Kaolin) Method

The clay bath method uses density differences between kernels and shells. A kaolin–water solution with controlled relative density ensures lighter kernels float while denser shells sink [3, 20]. However, this method introduces hygiene concerns, requires continuous agitation, and increases kernel moisture content, necessitating additional drying which may impact oil quality [15].

2.3.3 Dry Winnowing Column Systems

Multi-stage winnowing columns use controlled airflow to separate components by exploiting aerodynamic differences [5, 12]. They improve separation with optimized airflow rates and column geometry but require precise control and greater energy input.

2.3.4 Screening

Screening uses mechanical sieves to separate particles by size. Overlapping size distributions between kernels and shell fragments limit efficiency (~60–65%) [4].

2.3.5 Air Classification

Air classification separates materials based on aerodynamic response in upward airflow. Adjustable airflow rates allow optimization, but effectiveness depends strongly on particle size uniformity [8].

2.3.6 Blanket/Rug Method

The inclined rug separator exploits gravitational and frictional differences. Mixtures roll on a rotating inclined rug where lighter shells separate from heavier kernels due to differences in rolling behavior [10]. Effectiveness depends on rug angle, surface texture, and rotational speed.

2.4 Physical Characteristics of Palm Nut Components

Separation efficiency depends on the distinct physical properties of nut components. Average moisture contents are ~9.55% for kernels, 8.5% for shells, and 9.1% for whole nuts [16]. Key physical properties are summarized in Table 2.4.

	Component Mass (g)	Diameter (cm)	Density (g/cm ³)	Drag Coefficient (Cd)
Kernel	1.11	1.20	1.10	0.47 (approx.)
Shell	0.40	0.85	1.30	1.05 (approx.)
Nut	1.86	2.02	1.15	0.82 (approx.)

Morphological differences—smooth kernels versus irregular shells—affect aerodynamic drag and settling velocity, influencing separation based on airflow or projection mechanisms [16, 8].

2.5 Theoretical Foundation: Newtonian Mechanics and Aerodynamic Drag

The motion of palm nut components is governed by Newton’s Second Law:

$$F=ma$$

For projectile motion with air resistance, net force consists of gravitational force and aerodynamic drag. Quadratic drag is expressed as: $F_d = \frac{1}{2} C_d \rho A v^2$

where F_d is drag force, C_d is drag coefficient, ρ is air density, A is projected area, and v is velocity[8].

Differences in mass, projected area, and shape lead to different drag-to-mass ratios. When projected at controlled angles and velocities, kernels, shells, and nuts follow distinct trajectories, providing a theoretical basis for separation using aerodynamic forces.

2.6 Research Gap

Current separation methods rely on density, size, or friction but present limitations: wet systems introduce moisture challenges; screening has limited efficiency; conventional air classification depends on uniform particle size [5, 4]. There is limited research on controlled projectile motion under aerodynamic drag as a separation mechanism in palm kernel processing. Given measurable differences in physical and aerodynamic properties, projectile-based separation using drag principles represents a novel alternative with potential for improved efficiency, reduced moisture issues, and mechanical simplicity.

3. Methodology

3.1 Theoretical Framework

This study adopts an analytical approach based on Newtonian mechanics and aerodynamic drag theory to investigate the separation of palm nuts, kernels, and shells using the quadratic projectile drag principle. The separation concept is founded on the controlled projection of a cracked mixture from a discharge pipe inclined at an angle theta to the horizontal.

When the mixture emerges from the cracking chamber, a scooping mechanism propels the nuts, kernels, and shells into the atmosphere toward a horizontal deposition platform. Under the influence of gravity and aerodynamic drag, each component follows an independent trajectory. Because palm nuts, kernels, and shells differ in mass, size, projected area, and drag characteristics, their drag-to-mass ratios differ, leading to distinct velocity histories and landing positions.

Although ideal projectile motion neglects air resistance and produces a simple parabolic path, this assumption is unrealistic for lightweight agricultural particles such as palm kernel shells. Therefore, quadratic air drag was incorporated into the governing equations to more accurately describe particle motion in air. The drag force was assumed proportional to the square of velocity and acts opposite to the direction of motion.

Due to natural variations in size and mass, the landing positions of the components are expected to form zones centered around mean values rather than single discrete points. Different projection angles and velocities were evaluated to determine optimal separation conditions.

3.2 Governing Equations of Motion

The motion of each particle is governed by Newton's Second Law:
 $F = ma$

For projectile motion with quadratic drag, the drag force is expressed as:

$$F_D = \frac{1}{2} \rho C_D A v^2$$

where:

$$\rho = \text{air density} \left(1.2041 \frac{\text{kg}}{\text{m}^3} \right),$$

$C_D = \text{drag coefficient},$

$A = \text{projected area of the particle},$

$v = \text{instantaneous velocity}.$

The drag parameter (b) is defined as:

$$b = 1/2 \rho C_D A$$

and the projected area:

$$A = \frac{\pi d^2}{4}$$

where d is the equivalent diameter of the nut, kernel, or shell.

The gravitational acceleration used in the analysis was $g = 9.8 \text{m/s}^2$

The representative unit masses adopted were:

Palm nut: 0.00186 kg

Palm kernel: 0.00111 kg

Palm shell: 0.00040 kg

3.3 Motion in the Horizontal (x) Direction

For motion along the horizontal axis, only drag acts on the particle:

$$m\ddot{x} = -b\dot{x}$$

Rearranging:

$$\ddot{x} + \frac{b}{m} \dot{x} = 0$$

]Solving with the initial condition $\dot{x}(0) = u_x$, the horizontal displacement becomes:

$$x(t) = \frac{mu_x}{b} \left(1 - e^{\left\{-\frac{bt}{m}\right\}} \right)$$

This equation shows that horizontal velocity decays exponentially due to drag.

3.4 Motion in the Vertical (y) Direction

For vertical motion, both gravity and drag act:

$$m\ddot{y} = -mg - b\dot{y}$$

Rewriting:

$$\ddot{y} + \frac{b}{m}\dot{y} = -g$$

Solving the differential equation using complementary and particular solutions yields:

$$y(t) = \frac{m}{b} \left(v + \frac{mg}{b} \right) \left(1 - e^{\left\{-\frac{bt}{m}\right\}} \right) - \frac{mg}{b} t$$

where (v) is the initial vertical velocity component.

These expressions define the modified projectile trajectory under quadratic drag.

3.5 Simulation Procedure

The initial velocity components were defined as:

$$u_x = u \cos\theta$$

$$v = u \sin\theta$$

where (u) is the projection velocity and θ is the launch angle.

Simulations were conducted for selected projection velocities and angles. For each component (nut, kernel, and shell), the trajectory equations were evaluated to determine:

Horizontal displacement (range)

Landing position on the horizontal platform

The separation effectiveness was assessed based on the spatial distance between the mean landing zones of the nut, kernel, and shell.

For Velocity =10m/s, the graphical results are:

Plate 3.1 Combined Graph of y displacement in respect to x displacement for Nut, Kernel and shell @10° and velocity = 10m/s

Plate 3.2 Combined Graph of y displacement in respect to x displacement for Nut, Kernel and shell @ 20° and velocity = 10m/s

Plate 3.3 Combined Graph of y displacement in respect to x displacement for Nut, Kernel and shell @ 30° and velocity = 10m/s

Plate 3.4 Combined Graph of y displacement in respect to x displacement for Nut, Kernel and shell @40° and velocity = 10m/s

Plate 3.5 Combined Graph of y displacement in respect to x displacement for Nut, Kernel and shell @45⁰ and velocity = 10m/s

For Velocity = 15m/s, the combined graphical results are:

Plate 3.6 Combined Graph of y displacement in respect to x displacement for Nut, Kernel and shell @10⁰ and velocity = 15m/s

Plate 3.7 Combined Graph of y displacement in respect to x displacement for Nut, Kernel and shell @20⁰ and velocity = 15m/s

Plate 3.8 Combined Graph of y displacement in respect to x displacement for Nut, Kernel and shell @30⁰ and velocity = 15m/s

Plate 3.9 Combined Graph of y displacement in respect to x displacement for Nut, Kernel and shell @40⁰ and velocity = 15m/s

Plate 3.10 Combined Graph of y displacement in respect to x displacement for Nut, Kernel and shell @45⁰ and velocity = 15m/s

“Different angles of 10, 20, 30, 40 and 45 degrees, together with different velocities of 10 and 15m/s were investigated to ascertain the optimal angle and velocity for the best separation.”

3.2.2 Summary

These graphical analyses show that as both velocity and angle increase, the separation between nut, kernel, and shell improves. However, higher angles (especially 45°) result in greater trajectory spread, which requires more space.

The optimal condition balancing clear separation with minimal space requirement occurs at 30° and 15 m/s. At this point, the kernel and shell follow distinct paths without excessive displacement, making it the most space-efficient setup for effective separation.

4.0 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Introduction

The results of simulating the projectile motion of palm nut components kernel, shell, and whole nut under different launching angles and two initial velocities (10 m/s and 15 m/s) are presented in this chapter. The aim was to determine the optimal ejection angle and initial velocity for maximum spatial separation of the components using the quadratic projectile drag principle.

The simulation incorporated aerodynamic drag effects, enabling differentiation in flight paths based on mass, shape, and drag-to-mass ratio. The results are analyzed separately for each initial velocity.

4.2 Results at Initial Velocity of 10 m/s

The motion trajectories of the kernel, shell, and nut were plotted for launch angles of 10°, 20°, 30°, 40°, and 45°, with vertical displacement (y) versus horizontal displacement (x) illustrating the flight paths under air drag conditions.

4.2.1 Launch Angle = 10°

At this shallow angle, motion was largely horizontal with minimal vertical displacement. All components landed close together, resulting in poor spatial separation. Limited flight time reduced drag differentiation, producing significant trajectory overlap.

4.2.2 Launch Angle = 20°

Vertical displacement increased slightly, and the kernel began to lead marginally along the horizontal axis due to its lower mass and higher drag-to-mass interaction. However, overlap remained considerable, and separation was only moderate.

4.2.3 Launch Angle = 30°

A clearer distinction in trajectories emerged. The kernel traveled furthest, the shell fell earliest, and the nut followed an intermediate path. This demonstrates effective utilization of drag differences, producing fair separation.

4.2.4 Launch Angle = 40°

Spatial separation became more pronounced. All three components exhibited well-separated landing zones. Increased flight time enhanced aerodynamic differentiation, validating that longer drag interaction improves separation clarity.

4.2.5 Launch Angle = 45°

Maximum horizontal range occurred, but overlap between kernel and nut reappeared due to symmetry in projectile motion and longer hang time. While the shell dropped earlier, the overall differentiation decreased.

Summary at 10 m/s: Launch angles between 30° and 40° provided the best balance between range and separation, while 45° offered maximum distance but reduced component differentiation.

4.3 Results at Initial Velocity of 15 m/s

Increasing the initial velocity to 15 m/s intensified aerodynamic effects due to the quadratic dependence of drag on velocity.

4.3.1 Launch Angle = 10°

Although horizontal range increased, separation remained minimal. Components landed within a narrow band, indicating insufficient vertical displacement for drag-based sorting.

4.3.2 Launch Angle = 20°

The kernel began to separate more distinctly, while the shell experienced stronger drag deceleration and fell significantly short. Separation improved but was still moderate.

4.3.3 Launch Angle = 30°

Optimal separation occurred at this angle. The kernel achieved the longest trajectory, the nut landed at an intermediate distance, and the shell fell earliest. Flight paths were clearly distinguishable with minimal overlap, producing compact, well-defined landing zones.

4.3.4 Launch Angle = 40°

The kernel range increased further; however, overlap between kernel and nut began, and longer hang time caused partial convergence mid-air.

4.3.5 Launch Angle = 45°

While the kernel reached its maximum range, kernel and nut arcs overlapped. Complete separation remained possible but required more space, reducing efficiency.

Summary at 15 m/s: Launching at 30° provided the best compromise between drag-based separation and space efficiency, producing clear, orderly trajectories.

4.4 Validation of Results

The findings align with classical projectile motion theory and previous experimental studies:

1. Maximum horizontal range occurs at 45° in vacuum conditions. Simulations showed longest ranges at 45°, confirming consistency, while actual ranges were lower due to drag.
2. Trajectory ordering (kernel > nut > shell) matches aerodynamic principles; lower mass-to-drag ratios lead to greater deceleration and distinct flight behaviors.
3. Increasing velocity from 10 m/s to 15 m/s increased horizontal displacement and improved separation at optimal angles, consistent with kinetic energy scaling with (v²).

Minor discrepancies in optimal angles reported in literature likely stem from device-specific constraints. The current model represents ideal free-flight conditions governed by quadratic drag, providing theoretical optimization.

4.5 Summary of Results

Plate No.	Velocity (m/s)	Angle (°)	Separation Observed	Trajectory Overlap	Space Efficiency	Comments
3.2	10	10	Poor	High	Inefficient	Overlap in paths
3.3	10	20	Slight	Moderate	Moderate	Kernel starts diverging
3.4	10	30	Fair	Less	Better	Clear differentiation
3.5	10	40	Good	Low	Efficient	Distinct landing zones
3.6	10	45	Very good	Very low	Less efficient	Long range but spread out
3.7	15	10	Slight	Moderate	Moderate	Increased range
3.8	15	20	Moderate	Less	Better	Improved divergence

Plate No.	Velocity (m/s)	Angle (°)	Separation Observed	Trajectory Overlap	Space Efficiency	Comments
3.9	15	30	Good	Low	Most efficient	Optimal compact separation
3.10	15	40	Very good	Very low	Less efficient	Excessive spread
3.11	15	45	Excellent	None	Least efficient	Maximum spread, large space needed

Optimal Condition: Velocity = 15 m/s, Launch Angle = 30°—providing clear differentiation with minimal space.

4.6 Contribution to Knowledge and Nation

This study presents a novel application of projectile motion and quadratic drag to palm kernel separation, replacing traditional density-based or manual methods with aerodynamic sorting. The work bridges physics and agricultural engineering, linking drag equations to biological fragment behavior.

Practical advantages include:

Continuous dry separation without water

Reduced labor dependency

Improved kernel recovery efficiency

Enhanced throughput for small- and medium-scale mills

By optimizing kernel recovery, this system enhances oil yield, economic returns, and sustainability in palm-processing regions. Academically, it advances physics-based agricultural machinery design; economically, it supports modernization of palm kernel processing systems.

This version condenses repetitive descriptions, organizes sections clearly, and keeps all technical content, making it roughly 3.5 pages in standard academic formatting (12 pt font, double-spaced).

5.0 Conclusion

The application of quadratic projectile drag principles has successfully led to the design framework of a novel, non-contact palm kernel separation system.

Simulation results demonstrate that launching palm nut fragments at 30° with an initial velocity of 15 m/s provides the most effective spatial separation. This condition ensures clear categorization of kernel, nut, and shell based on distinct flight paths while maintaining compact space requirements. The study confirms that aerodynamic differentiation can be reliably harnessed for agricultural processing applications and provides a solid theoretical foundation for the development of efficient palm nut separator machines.

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